

Fetomaternal Outcomes Following Sub-Lingual and Vaginal Misoprostol for Induction of Labour: A Randomized Controlled Trial

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ABSTRACT

Background: Induction of labour may become necessary to avert adverse obstetric outcomes in the course of pregnancy. The appropriate dosage and route for misoprostol administration for induction of labour is not well understood in our clinical setting. In our setting no studies have been carried out to compare the efficacy and safety of sub-lingual and vaginal misoprostol.

Aim: To compare the fetomaternal outcome of events using the sub-lingual and vaginal routes for induction of labour.

Methodology: One hundred and forty pregnant women at term who fulfill the inclusion criteria were equally randomized into the two arms of the study to receive either 25 µg of misoprostol sublingually or 25µg vaginally and fetal outcomes were compared in the two arms of the study.

Results: The fetal and maternal outcome was not statistically significant between the vaginal and sublingual groups. The perinatal outcomes between the sublingual and vaginal misoprostol groups showed no statistically significant differences. Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes were similar, with few babies scoring below 7 at 1 minute and improving by 5 minutes. Neonatal intensive care unit admission was more common in the sublingual than vaginal group, but the difference was not significant. The main indications for neonatal intensive care unit admission were birth asphyxia, sepsis, and respiratory distress, with no significant difference between groups. Maternal side effects were comparable between the two groups, with no statistically significant differences across all parameters. Although the vaginal misoprostol group showed slightly higher frequencies of nausea, shivering, flushing, tachysystole, and hyperstimulation, these differences did not reach statistical significance ($P > 0.05$).

Conclusion: The sublingual and vaginal routes for administration of misoprostol for induction of labour showed comparable fetomaternal outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Fetomaternal outcome, Misoprostol, Vaginal, Sublingual, Induction of labour.

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INTRODUCTION

Labour induction is a medical intervention that involves artificially stimulating uterine contractions before they begin naturally, leading to cervical effacement and dilatation, with the goal of achieving a safe vaginal delivery^{1, 2}. This procedure is considered when the risks associated with

continuing the pregnancy outweigh the risks of intervening³. Labour induction has been a part of obstetric practice for decades, but its usage has increased significantly in recent years, with approximately 9.6% of global deliveries being medically induced⁴. In the United States these rates are considerably higher reaching approximately 27%, while in

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Europe they seem to range between 6.8 and 33%.^{5,6}

Various methods are used to induce cervical ripening and labour, including oxytocin, prostaglandins, laminaria tents, and Foley balloon catheters, with prostaglandins and oxytocin being the most widely accepted⁷. Labour induction is a common procedure in obstetrics, involving medical or surgical initiation of uterine contractions before spontaneous labour begins^{8,9}. Although the exact mechanisms are unclear, cervical ripening is known to precede labour onset, and an unfavourable cervix reduces the likelihood of a successful vaginal delivery¹⁰⁻¹². The bishop score is inversely correlated with labour duration, and cervical status significantly influences induction success¹³⁻¹⁵. An unripe cervix that is bishop score of less than 6 makes surgical amniotomy challenging and increases the risk of prolonged labour, maternal and fetal complications, and caesarean section when oxytocin is used^{1,2,13-15}.

Achieving cervical ripening is crucial for successful labour induction, particularly in women with an unfavourable cervix. Induction of labour with an unripe cervix is linked to prolonged labour, increased instrumental deliveries, and higher Caesarean section rates compared to spontaneous labour or induction with a favourable cervix. Also, an increase in instrumental deliveries and a higher rate of caesarean sections are seen in unfavourable cervix^{12,13}. Various methods have been employed to induce cervical ripening and labour. Pharmacological agents used for cervical ripening and labour induction include prostaglandins, mifepristone, and relaxin^{7,10-13}.

The American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists recommend using prostaglandins for cervical ripening and labour induction, with doses spaced at least 3-6 hours apart to minimize the risk of uterine tachysystole¹⁶. However, the optimal interval between doses has not been standardized. The World Health Organization suggests using misoprostol for labour induction, either orally (25 mcg, 2-hourly orally or 25 mcg, 6-hourly vaginally⁴). According to a meta-analysis by Alfirevic *et al*¹⁷, combining misoprostol with oxytocin and amniotomy is the most effective method for achieving vaginal delivery within 24 hours.

Using higher doses or shorter intervals of misoprostol increases the risk of side effects, including hyper-stimulation syndrome defined as contractions lasting longer than 90 seconds or more than 5 contractions in 10 minutes, tachysystole defined as 6 or more contractions in 10 minutes for 2 consecutive periods, and hypersystole which is a single contraction of at least 2 minutes^{12,13}. Other potential complications include hyperpyrexia, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, uterine rupture, fetal distress, and demise¹⁰⁻¹⁴. Several articles have addressed the efficacy of the various routes of misoprostol in inducing a successful vaginal delivery and a previous meta-analysis that was published in 2008 suggested that both sublingual and vaginal routes seem to be comparable in terms of achieving vaginal delivery.^{1,16}

Since then, several randomized trials have been published and an update is indicated to review current knowledge as, to date, there is no consensus on the optimal route of misoprostol intake for induction of labour. The purpose of this study is to compare sublingual and vaginal misoprostol administration in inducing labour in terms of on maternal and neonatal outcomes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A single-center, non-inferiority, parallel, open labelled, randomized controlled trial (RCT). Randomization was into two equal arms. Participants were parturients undergoing induction of labour at the Federal Medical Center Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. All procedures followed the 2013 Helsinki Declaration. The research ethics committee, Federal Medical Center Yenagoa approved the trial protocol. Each participant gave written informed consent to participate. Exclusion criteria included women who refusal to give consent, immunosuppression, previous uterine scar, antepartum hemorrhage, hypersensitivity to misoprostol and oxytocin, intrauterine fetal death and macrosomia.

INTERVENTION

All pregnant women at term that meets the inclusion criteria was randomized into Group A and B respectively. An astute vaginal examination was done to assess the bishop score. Then participants in Group A had twenty-five micrograms of misoprostol placed sublingually every six hours for a maximum of four doses or onset of labour. Fetal heart rate and uterine activity were monitored continuously for at least half an hour after misoprostol application. Then participants in Group A were placed in dorsal position, vulva cleaned with diluted chlorhexidine solution and aseptic procedure ensured. Twenty-five micrograms of misoprostol was placed intravaginally at the posterior vaginal fornix every six hours for a maximum of four doses or onset of labour. Fetal heart rate and uterine activity was monitored continuously for at least half an hour after misoprostol application before the patient was allowed to ambulate.

Both Group A and B participants will have a vaginal examination done every 6 hours until onset of labour.

When active phase parameters are achieved oxytocin (Pitocin) augmentation was commenced following amniotomy if required. A minimum interval of six hours is recommended after the last misoprostol dose before augmentation.

Technique for Performing Amniotomy

The patient was placed in dorsal position, vulva cleaned with diluted chlorhexidine solution and aseptic procedure ensured. A pelvic examination was performed to evaluate the cervix and station of the presenting part. The fetal heart rate was recorded before and after the procedure. Cord presentation was checked. An amniohook was inserted through the cervical os and by sliding it along the middle and index fingers (hook side toward the hand). The membranes were

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ruptured. The examining fingers was used to guide the fetal head ensuring gradual release of amniotic fluid in order to prevent sudden decompression.

The nature of the amniotic fluid was recorded (clear, bloody, thick or thin meconium). Amniotomy was performed by doctors. Labour was strictly monitored by the use of a partograph to avoid prolonged labour and to institute intervention where necessary. The outcome of labour was recorded on the partograph.

PRIMARY OUTCOME MEASURES

The primary outcome was neonatal outcomes such as intrapartum meconium passage, intrapartum fetal death, Apgar scores and admission to the neonatal intensive care unit.

SECONDARY OUTCOME MEASURES

Secondary outcomes including the rates of Caesarean sections and maternal side effects.

SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

The calculated minimum sample size to achieve a statistical power of 80% and 5% significant level was 62. A deliberate oversampling of 10% was allowed for nonresponders/dropouts. This gave an approximate of 70 parturient on each arm of the study.

RECRUITMENT

Patients were enrolled into the study in order of appearance, based on their eligibility and willingness to participate in the study (convenience sampling). All women being prepared for induction of labour were met by the researcher or trained assistant in the antenatal ward or labour ward. Exclusion criteria were identified through relevant information obtained from case folders and history obtained from the women. To obtain an informed consent, the researcher or a trained assistant explained the aim and processes of the study and its benefits to eligible women in simple and clear terms, and an assurance of safety was given. Participants signed the consent form for the study only after they have expressed an understanding of the study and showed willingness to participate.

RANDOMIZATION AND ALLOCATION CONCEALMENT MECHANISM

Allocation sequence generation

Using the WINPEPI software for randomization, a random and balanced allocation of numbers 1 to 140 to Group A and B will be conducted. The women will be allocated to receive either Twenty-five microgram of misoprostol sublingually (Group A) or intravaginally (Group B).

Allocation concealment mechanism

Identical, sealed, sequentially arranged and opaque envelopes with cards inscribed with letter A or B concealed within them according to the randomly assigned letter to each number

from 1 to 140. These envelopes will also be labelled outwardly using serial numbers from 1 to 140.

Implementation

As each eligible woman is received into the antenatal ward or labour ward for induction of labour, a research assistant picks an envelope according to the sequence. The letter inscribed on the card in the envelope will be announced and shown to the researcher and nurse. The serial number / identification number on the envelope selected will be attached to the case folder and other documents for the study.

Data collection methods

The primary and secondary outcome measures were obtained using a purpose designed proforma.

Data management

SPSS spreadsheet was used for data management. Data entry from paper data collection instruments into the SPSS spreadsheet was done weekly.

Data Monitoring

Full compliance with the trial monitoring mechanism of the study Centre was ensured.

DATA ANALYSIS

An intention-to-treat (ITT) analysis will be employed. Statistical analysis of the data obtained from the study was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Frequencies and percentages of categorical data was determined. Mean and standard deviation of continuous numerical data, median, mode and range of discrete numerical data was determined. Continuous data was assessed for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Comparisons between experimental and control groups was done using Chi-square test of proportions for categorical data, Student 't' test for normally distributed continuous data and Mann-Whitney U test for non-normally distributed continuous data. A non-inferiority margin of 2 was set between experimental group to control group. A p-value < 0.05 will be considered significant statistically.

RESULTS

One hundred and forty-nine women were booked for induction of labour at the Obstetrics and Gynaecology department of Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa. However, nine of these women declined to participate in the study. One hundred and forty women were ultimately enrolled in the study and randomly assigned to one of two study arms in a 1:1 ratio. The two arms consisted of group A and B respectively. In the group A, 70 women were assigned to receive the intervention and were assessed for primary and secondary outcome measures. In the group B, 70 women were assigned to receive the intended intervention and were assessed for primary and secondary outcome measures. Consequently, data from all 140 enrolled women were included in the final analysis.

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Figure 1: Study Flow Diagram

Table 1: Sociodemographic data of participants

		Group				X ²	P-value
		A		B			
		N	%	n	%		
Age	<20 years	8	11.6%	8	11.3%	0.05	.99
	21 – 30years	30	43.5%	30	42.3%		
	31 – 40years	23	33.3%	25	35.2%		
	>40years	8	11.6%	8	11.3%		
	Mean Age		30 ± 8		31 ± 7		
Tribe	Ijaw	17	24.6%	21	29.6%	1.09	.89
	Urhobo	17	24.6%	13	18.3%		
	Igbo	14	20.3%	14	19.7%		
	Yoruba	11	15.9%	13	18.3%		
	Others	10	14.5%	10	14.1%		
Educational Status	Primary	23	33.3%	11	15.5%	6.21	.10
	Secondary	11	15.9%	16	22.5%		
	Tertiary	15	21.7%	20	28.2%		
	Post graduate	20	29.0%	24	33.8%		

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The demographic characteristics of the participants in the two groups sublingual misoprostol (Group A) and vaginal misoprostol (Group B) were similar and showed no statistically significant differences. The mean age was 30 ± 8 years in Group A and 31 ± 7 years in Group B, with the majority in the 21–30 years age range. Ethnic distribution across Ijaw, Urhobo, Igbo, Yoruba, and other tribes was

comparable ($P = .89$). Although there were variations in educational status with Group A having a higher percentage with primary education and Group B having more with postgraduate education these differences were not statistically significant ($P = .10$). This suggests that both groups were demographically well-matched at baseline.

Table 2: Obstetrics profile of participants

		Group				X ²	P-value
		A		B			
		N	%	N	%		
Parity	Para 0	8	11.4%	12	17.1%	2.43	.65
	Para 1	15	21.4%	15	21.4%		
	Para 2	15	21.4%	11	15.7%		
	Para 3	16	22.9%	12	17.1%		
	Para 4	16	22.9%	20	28.6%		
	Total	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		
Gestation	37 weeks	10	14.3%	13	18.6%	2.98	.56
	38 weeks	17	24.3%	16	22.9%		
	39 weeks	16	22.9%	9	12.9%		
	40 weeks	12	17.1%	16	22.9%		
	41 weeks	15	21.4%	16	22.9%		
	Total	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		
	Mean GA	39 ±1 weeks		39 ±1 weeks			
Booking	Booked	35	50.0%	40	57.1%	0.71	.39
	Unbooked	35	50.0%	30	42.9%		
	Total	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		

The obstetric characteristics of both groups were similar. Parity and gestational age distributions showed no significant differences ($P = .65$ and $P = .56$, respectively), with most participants between Para 1–4 and at term (mean GA 39 ± 1

weeks). Booking status was also comparable, with 50.0% in Group A and 57.1% in Group B booked for antenatal care ($P = .39$).

Table 3: The mode of delivery following induction of labour

		Group				X ²	P-value
		A		B			
		N	%	n	%		
Mode of Delivery	Spontaneous vaginal delivery	59	84.3%	56	80.0%	0.34	.84
	Assisted Vaginal Delivery	2	2.8%	3	4.3%		
	Caesarean section	9	12.9%	11	15.7%		

The mode of delivery was also similar across both groups, with spontaneous vaginal delivery being the most common (84.3% in Group A vs. 80.0% in Group B), followed by

assisted vaginal delivery and caesarean section, with no significant difference ($P = .84$).

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Table 4: Safety of two different routes of misoprostol (sublingual and vaginal) administered for induction of labour

		Group				X ²	P-value
		A		B			
		N	%	N	%		
APH	No	69	98.6%	68	97.1%	0.34	.55
	Yes	1	1.4%	2	2.9%		
	Total	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		
PPH	No	66	94.3%	65	92.9%	0.11	.73
	Yes	4	5.7%	5	7.1%		
	Total	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		
Blood loss >500mls	No	66	94.3%	65	92.9%	0.11	.73
	Yes	4	5.7%	5	7.1%		
	Total	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		
Need for transfusion	No	66	94.3%	65	92.9%	0.11	.73
	Yes	4	5.7%	5	7.1%		
	Total	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		
Uterine rupture	No	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		
	Yes	0	0.0%	0	0.0%		
	Total	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		
Cervical laceration	No	66	94.3%	62	88.6%	0.64	.42
	Yes	4	5.7%	8	11.4%		
	Total	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		
Vaginal laceration	No	59	84.3%	37	52.9%	0.64	.37
	Yes	11	15.7%	33	47.1%		
	Total	70	100.0%	70	100.0%		

The safety outcomes for sublingual (Group A) and vaginal (Group B) misoprostol were largely comparable, with no statistically significant differences observed across all parameters. Rates of antepartum hemorrhage (1.4% vs. 2.9%, P = .55), postpartum hemorrhage (5.7% vs. 7.1%, P = .73), blood loss over 500 ml, and need for transfusion were similar

in both groups. Uterine rupture did not occur in either group. The rates of cervical (5.7% vs. 11.4%) and vaginal lacerations (15.7% vs. 47.1%) were also higher in the vaginal group but without statistical significance. Overall, both routes of administration showed a comparable safety profile.

Table 5: Comparison of the perinatal outcome in the two different groups

		Group				Test	P-value
		A		B			
		N	%	n	%		
Apgar_1min	<7	10	14.3%	12	17.1%	6.21 ^a	.71
	>7	60	85.7%	58	82.9%		
Apgar_5min	<7	7	10.0%	9	12.9%	8.29 ^a	.50
	>7	63	90.0%	61	87.1%		
Birth Weight	Mean Birth weight	3.40 ± 0.70		3.2 ± 0.72		1.98 ^b	.05
NICU Admission	No	63	90.0%	61	87.1%	1.83 ^a	.17
	Yes	7	10.0%	9	12.9%		
NICU admission indication	Birth Asphyxia	3	4.3%	5	7.1%		

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Sepsis	1	1.4%	2	2.8%		
Respiratory distress	3	4.3%	2	4.3%	2.77 ^a	.42

a – chi-square; b – student t-test

The perinatal outcomes between the sublingual (Group A) and vaginal (Group B) misoprostol groups showed no statistically significant differences. Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes were similar, with few babies scoring below 7 at 1 minute (85.7% in Group A vs. 82.9% in Group B; $P = .71$) and improving by 5 minutes ($P = .50$). The mean birth weight was slightly higher in Group A (3.40 ± 0.70 kg) than in Group

B (3.2 ± 0.72 kg), with statistical significance ($P = .05$). NICU admission was less common in Group A (10.0%) than in Group B (12.9%), but the difference was not significant ($P = .17$). The main indications for NICU admission were birth asphyxia, sepsis, and respiratory distress, with no significant difference between groups ($P = .42$). Overall, perinatal outcomes were largely comparable between the two groups.

Table 6: Comparison of Maternal Side Effects Between Sublingual and Vaginal Misoprostol

Maternal Side Effect	Sublingual Group N(%)	Vaginal Group N(%)	χ^2	P-value
Nausea	5 (7.1)	7 (10.0)	0.45	0.50
Vomiting	2 (2.9)	3 (4.3)	0.21	0.65
Shivering	4 (5.7)	6 (8.6)	0.55	0.46
Flushing	3 (4.3)	4 (5.7)	0.16	0.69
Uterine Hyperstimulation	1 (1.4)	2 (2.9)	0.34	0.56
Tachysystole	1 (1.4)	2 (2.9)	0.34	0.56

Maternal side effects were comparable between the two groups, with no statistically significant differences across all parameters. Although the vaginal misoprostol group showed slightly higher frequencies of nausea, fever, flushing, tachysystole, and hyperstimulation, these differences did not reach statistical significance ($P > 0.05$). Overall, both routes demonstrated a similar safety profile.

DISCUSSION

The study showed no statistically significant difference ($P = 0.84$) in mode of delivery between the two groups; spontaneous vaginal delivery was the most frequent outcome (84.2% in Group A versus 80.0% in Group B), followed by Caesarean section and assisted vaginal delivery. No significant difference in vaginal delivery rates was observed between women receiving vaginal misoprostol and those receiving sublingual misoprostol, though a slightly higher number of vaginal deliveries occurred in the sublingual group. These findings are consistent with the results reported by Chhatani *et al*¹⁷. However, they conflict with the study by Ifarinola *et al*¹⁸, which used a 4-hourly dosing interval and found different outcomes.

The current study revealed no statistically significant difference in the rate of Caesarean section between the vaginal misoprostol group (15.7%) and the sublingual misoprostol group (12.9%), despite a slightly higher proportion of Caesarean deliveries in the vaginal group. This finding aligns with results from Chhatani *et al*¹⁷, who studied 75 patients per subgroup and reported Caesarean section rates of 18.67% in the sublingual group and 29.33% in the vaginal group. Similarly, Madhu *et al*¹⁹ compared sublingual versus vaginal misoprostol for labour induction and found cesarean

section rates of 12% in the sublingual group and 14% in the vaginal group. The tendency toward a higher Caesarean rate in the vaginal misoprostol group may reflect the greater uterotonic potency of vaginal misoprostol, which can induce changes in fetal heart rate, a common indication for Caesarean delivery in this study. However, this observation conflicts with the findings of Jahromi *et al*²⁰ in Iran, who used a 4-hour dosing interval.

The study found no significant difference in Apgar scores at first minute and fifth minute between the vaginal misoprostol group and the sublingual misoprostol group, likely because both groups received the same dose and timing of misoprostol administration. This result is consistent with the findings of Nimbark *et al*⁹ in India, who used 50 micrograms of misoprostol. However, the result differs from Feitosa *et al*²¹, who reported abnormal Apgar score changes in the sublingual group, possibly due to methodological differences, as their study was multicenter. In the present study, a higher number of neonates in the sublingual group required admission to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit compared with the vaginal group, though the difference was not statistically significant. This finding supports the results of Jahromi *et al*²⁰, but contrasts with Okonkwo *et al*²², who observed more Neonatal Intensive Care Unit admissions in the vaginal group.

The maternal complications, nausea, vomiting, flushing, and shivering were observed to be marginally more frequent in the vaginal misoprostol group compared with the sublingual group, though the difference did not reach statistical significance. The gastrointestinal side-effects may represent the wide range of response to misoprostol in different women. This finding aligns with the study by Okonkwo *et al*²², and

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may be attributable to the higher bioavailability of vaginal misoprostol relative to sublingual administration.

However, the result contradicts the findings of Ayati *et al*⁸, likely because of racial differences between the study populations. Additionally, uterine hyperstimulation and tachysystole occurred more often in the vaginal group than in the sublingual group, although the difference was not statistically significant. This was similar to a study by Okonkwo *et al*²² but at variance with Zahran *et al*²³, who reported a higher incidence of hyperstimulation and tachysystole in the sublingual group, possibly because their study included a larger sample size.

No maternal deaths, uterine ruptures, or neonatal deaths occurred in the current study, mirroring other reports^{18, 22}. This safety outcome likely stems from adherence to a strict protocol using a 25 micrograms dose of misoprostol as recommended by the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists for induction of labour, a 6-hour dosing interval, and avoidance of oxytocin augmentation within 4 hours of the last misoprostol dose.

STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS: The study used primary data, which gave precise information. The randomized clinical trial design of this study gives a high level of evidence and also reduces bias. Bias was reduced by randomization.

The study followed an appropriate randomization protocol but could not incorporate blinding of subjects and caregivers in the study. The study did not assess the patient satisfaction rate with the different routes, which could have offered insight into the patient's preference to a particular route. Additionally, this study's findings may not be generalizable to other populations, as it was conducted exclusively among women undergoing induction of labour at a single hospital, the Federal Medical Centre Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

CONCLUSION

The sublingual and vaginal routes for administration of misoprostol showed comparable fetomaternal outcomes devoid of significant side effects.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that sublingual misoprostol can be used just as the vaginal misoprostol for induction of labour at the Federal Medical Centre Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. To further validate and generalize these findings, larger, multicenter studies using a similar protocol are suggested which will further increase external validity.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Idea/Concept: Atemie Gordon, Harry T. Clement;
Design: Atemie Gordon, Harry T. Clement, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Okumoko A Maureen;

Control/Supervision: Atemie Gordon, Warisuo S. Ariwelo, Nwanze C Nnamdi; Data Collection and/or Processing: Atemie Gordon, Warisuo S. Ariwelo, Nwanze C Nnamdi, Okumoko A Maureen; Analysis and/or Interpretation: Atemie Gordon, Akanatei I Daniel, Ani C MaryJane; Literature Review: Atemie Gordon, Nwanze C Nnamdi, Akanatei I Daniel; Writing the Article: Atemie Gordon; Critical Review: Atemie Gordon, Harry T. Clement, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Ani C MaryJane, Warisuo S. Ariwelo, Nwanze C Nnamdi, Akanatei I Daniel, Okumoko A Maureen.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethical committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

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